

Effects of annealing temperature on properties of SiO₂ nanoparticles for supercapacitor applications

J.Thenmozhi¹, E.Kavitha^{2*}, N.Sundaraganesan³

¹*Department of Physics, Annamalai University, Annamalainagar-608002, Tamilnadu, India.*

²*Department of Physics, NRK Govt Arts College for Women, Namakkal-637001, Tamilnadu, India.*

³*Department of Physics, Annamalai University, Annamalainagar-608002, Tamilnadu, India.*

* Corresponding Author

Dr. E.Kavitha

Assistant Professor

Department of Physics,

NRK Govt Arts College for Women,

Namakkal-637001,

Tamilnadu, India.

Cell: +91-8637430882

Abstract

In this work, a sol-gel method for preparing nanosized SiO₂ for supercapacitor applications. Tetraethyl orthosilicate was used as precursor and PVP as surfactant for the synthesis of SiO₂ nanoparticles. The effect of annealing temperature on prepared SiO₂ nanoparticles (NPs) was examined through the thermal, structural, morphological, and electrochemical characteristics. The thermal properties of as-prepared SiO₂ nanoparticles were evaluated using TG-DTA analysis. The X-ray diffraction result suggested that the prepared nanoparticles had amorphous structure and the average crystallite size decreased with increasing annealing temperatures. The SEM micrographs showed the SiO₂ NPs appeared as an aggregated bundle-like structure. The EDX analysis confirmed the existence of elements of Si and O. The

oxidation and reduction peaks revealed that the SiO₂ NPs had a supercapacitor nature by cyclic voltammetry and achieved high specific capacitance value of 356 Fg⁻¹ at scan rate of 5 mV/s. These findings suggest that SiO₂ NPs, which offer a cost-effective and scalable approach, are promising candidates for supercapacitor electrodes

Keywords: Supercapacitor, Pseudocapacitor, annealing temperature, SiO₂ NPs.

1. Introduction

The scientific world has focused a great deal of interest on silica nanoparticles because of its numerous uses in drugs, electronics, insulators, and catalysis. The oxide nanoparticles produced using various techniques have well electrical, optical, magnetic, thermal energy storage, solar energy conversion, and as additives in nanofluids they seem to be more beneficial [1-4]. There has been a lot of interest in silica nanoparticles for use in pigments, drugs, catalysis, and medicines [5]. The materials substrates, humidity sensors, electrical insulators, thermal insulators, and electronic substrates are all made with amorphous SiO₂ nanoparticles. Each of these products has a distinct function for the silica particles. Some of these goods quality is significantly influenced by the size and spatial dispersion of the particles of silica [6]. High-purity silica particles with a narrow size distribution are crucial because high-tech industries like biotechnology and photonics are increasing their demand for these materials [7]. Regarding surface defects associated with large surface/volume ratios, Si nanoparticles can be obtained among respect to their structural, functional, morphological and optical characteristics [8]. Silica nanoparticles are prepared by a variety of methods, including as sol-gel processing, combustion synthesis, hydrothermal processes, chemical vapour deposition, micro emulsion

processing, and plasma synthesis [9]. The primary objective was to regulate the size, shape, and surface reactivity of the particles regardless of the synthesis method. The most widely used method for synthesis silica nanoparticles is the sol-gel procedure, which involves the metal alkoxides simultaneous hydrolysis and condensation reaction. Along with numerous techniques, the sol-gel approach offers a few benefits, including low temperature synthesis and chemical composition-based reaction kinetics control [10 - 12]. Mesoporous silica nanospheres that were synthesized using various cationic surfactants and polyvinyl pyrrolidone were reported to have homogeneous size and shape [13]. Many benefits of the sol-gel process over other approaches include its convenience, adaptability, purity, homogeneity, and changes of by altering the synthesis parameters, material qualities [14].

2. Preparation of silicon dioxide (SiO₂) nanoparticles

The sol-gel technique was used to synthesis SiO₂ nanoparticles. There was no need for additional purification because every reagent utilized was analytical grade. In this work, we have used tetraethylorthosilicate (99.9%, Aldrich), absolute ethanol (EtOH 99.5%, Aldrich), Glycolic acid (EMPULRA), and Polyvinylpyrrolidone PVP (LOBA). Glycolic acid (2.3 ml) was added to a stirred solution of Tetraethylorthosilicate (TEOS) (2.2 ml), and the stirring was left for ten minutes. To create sol, slowly add 12 ml of a 5 weight percent PVP solution in ethanol was added drop wise to above solution and the mixture was allowed to stir for one hour in order form the sol. The sol turned into a gel after a full day of ageing. The gel was dried at 100 °C 1 for hour in order to evaporate water and organic compounds. After drying, SiO₂ product was annealed at different temperature (500 °C, 600 °C, 700 °C and 800 °C) and grained to obtain fine white colored nanoparticles. After annealed, the prepared samples were characterized using Thermo gravimetric analysis (TG-DTA), X-Ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier Transform Infrared

Spectroscopy (FT-IR), Scanning electron microscope (SEM-EDX) and Cyclic Voltammetry (CV).

Fig. 1. Synthesis process of SiO₂ nanoparticles.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Thermal analysis (TG-DTA)

The thermal analysis of as-prepared SiO₂ nanoparticles was studied by TG-DTA analysis. In order to do that, curves were recorded in the nitrogen environment between ambient temperatures to 1000 °C, increasing at a rate of 20 °C per minute. The TG/DTA curve for SiO₂ nanoparticles are shown in Fig. 2. It is evident from the figure, the TG curve showed the three stages of weight loss. The desorption of the sample water content may be the cause of the first weight loss seen below 180 °C. It's possible that the breakdown of organic and inorganic templates leading to the final product's crystallization is the cause of the anticipated final weight loss in the 190 – 390 °C range. The final weight loss brought on by the SiO₂ nanoparticles

formation at temperatures between 370 - 480 °C. An endothermic peak observed at 240 °C is shown in the DTA curve, was corresponded to water content is degrading. On the other hand, the formation of SiO₂ nanoparticles and the thermal breakdown of glycolic acid the cause of the exothermic peak that appears at 535 °C [15-19].

Fig. 2 TG/DTA curve of SiO₂ nanoparticles.

3.2. Structural analysis (XRD)

As seen in Fig. 3, the X-ray diffraction patterns verified that the produced SiO₂ samples were amorphous. The broad peak displays a whole amorphous structure. The large peak in the XRD pattern verifies that the produced SiO₂ nanoparticles are amorphous. With the exception of a broad band centered at 22.67°, 22.21°, 21.27° and 20.85° for sample annealed at 500, 600, 700 and 800°C, respectively. The obtained results indicated that amorphous nature of SiO₂ nanoparticles, there is no diffraction peak. There is no impurity peak for SiO₂ nanoparticles when the findings are compared to the JCPDS file for SiO₂ [4, 20 & 21].

Fig. 3. XRD pattern of SiO₂ nanoparticles with different annealing temperatures.

Using the Scherrer equation, the XRD line broadening data was used to calculate the particles' crystalline size.

$$D = K\lambda / (\beta \cos \theta) \quad (1)$$

Where, λ is the wavelength of CuK α radiation (1.5406 Å), β is full width half maximum (FWHM) of the (hkl) planes, and θ is bragg's diffraction angle by matching the database of the JCPDS file No. 89-1667, the diffraction peaks from Fig. 3 indicate a monoclinic phase structure with a small crystalline size. The average crystalline size of SiO₂ nanoparticles is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Average Crystallite size of SiO₂ at different annealing temperatures.

S.No	Annealing Temperature (°C)	Average Crystalline Size D (nm)
1	500	61
2	600	59
3	700	42
4	800	34

3.3 Functional group analysis (FT-IR)

Fig. 4. FT-IR spectrum of SiO₂ nanoparticles at different annealing temperatures.

FT-IR spectra of SiO₂ NPs with various annealing temperatures such as 500 °C, 600 °C, 700 °C and 800 °C were measured wavelength range of 4000 and 400 cm⁻¹ are shown in Fig. 4. The presence of O-H stretching bond, which are seen in the region at 1649 to 1669 cm⁻¹ [22-24]. The bands, which represents the stretch and asymmetric vibration of Si-O-Si, observed at 1037 to 1065 cm⁻¹. The stretching modes of Si-OH, both symmetric and asymmetric, are responsible for the infrared bands located at 1048 cm⁻¹, 1040 cm⁻¹, 1066 cm⁻¹, and 1047 cm⁻¹. The peak appears at 796 cm⁻¹, 781 cm⁻¹, 802 cm⁻¹, and 789 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the stretching and deformation of CH₂ in addition to the hydroxyl groups. Furthermore, the stretching vibration of the metal-oxygen Si-O bond is represented by the transmission band, which has a centre at 433 cm⁻¹, 439 cm⁻¹, 436 cm⁻¹, and 443 cm⁻¹ [25 & 26].

3.4 Morphological analysis (SEM-EDX)

Fig. 5.1. SEM-EDX Micrograph of SiO₂ nanoparticles annealed at 500 °C

Fig. 5.2. SEM-EDX Micrograph of SiO₂ nanoparticles annealed at 600 °C

Fig. 5.3. SEM-EDX Micrograph of SiO₂ nanoparticles annealed at 700 °C

Fig. 5.4. SEM-EDX micrograph of SiO₂ nanoparticles annealed at 800 °C

Through SEM investigation, the SiO₂ nanoparticles morphology was examined. The SiO₂ nanoparticles of SEM micrographs annealed at different temperatures, like 500 °C, 600°C, 700°C and 800°C are displayed in Figs. 5.1 – Figs. 5.4. As observed in the SEM images, the prepared particles are formed aggregated bundle like morphology. According to SEM pictures, the particles range in size from 1µm to 500 nm. Further, increasing the annealing temperature the bundle like morphology changed to spherical particles [27]. A significant number of individual, tiny nanoparticles and agglomerates are present. The EDX spectrum confirmed the presence of elements like Si and O [28 & 29].

3.5 Electrochemical property (CV)

Fig. 6. CV curves of SiO₂ nanoparticles at different scan rates.

The electrochemical property of SiO₂ NPs was studied by using CV analysis. From the CV curves of SiO₂ NPs were recorded at different scan rates (5, 10, 25, 50 and 100 mV/s) in the potential window of -1.5 to +1.5 V and presented in Fig. 6. However, the deviation in the rectangular shape of the curve implies that the sample is having pseudocapacitive nature [30]. From the figure, it is observed that for the entire range of scanning, the sample shows the presence of both oxidation and reduction peaks revealing the pseudocapacitive nature of the sample. Such behavior can be described to reversible electrochemical reactions. Additionally, the potential of the anodic and cathodic peaks is seen to shift in less positive and more negative directions, as the scan rate increases [31]. The inability of the ion diffusion rate to adequately counterbalance the electronic naturalization that takes place during the redox process. The specific capacitance (Cs) of the sample can be approximated using the equation [32],

$$C_s = \frac{Q}{\Delta v \cdot m} \quad (2)$$

Where, Q is the average internal area, Δv is the working Voltage potential range (V) and m is mass of the electrode materials.

The specific capacitance of the synthesized SiO₂ nanoparticles was determined using equation (1), and the results are presented in Table 2. The data indicates that at a scan rate of 5 mVs⁻¹, the samples exhibited peak capacitance values of 310 Fg⁻¹, 325 Fg⁻¹, 356 Fg⁻¹, and 340 Fg⁻¹ for the samples annealed at temperatures of 500 °C, 600 °C, 700 °C and 800 °C, respectively. Nevertheless, it is observed that this capacitance value diminishes progressively with an increase in the scan rate. The elevated specific capacitance of SiO₂ suggests its potential applicability in supercapacitor technologies [33-36].

Table. 2 Specific capacitance values of SiO₂ nanoparticles at different scan rates

Scan rate (mV/s)	Specific capacitance (F/g) 500 °C	Specific capacitance (F/g) 600 °C	Specific capacitance (F/g) 700 °C	Specific capacitance (F/g) 800 °C
5	310	325	356	340
10	258	261	271	223
25	96	101	129	93
50	54	57	68	51
75	56	53	60	48
100	26	33	36	29

4. Conclusion

The sol-gel approach was effectively used to synthesize and characterize SiO₂ nanoparticles. From the TG-DTA analysis, the endothermic peak at about (240 °C) and exothermic (480 °C) reveals the formation of SiO₂ nanoparticles. A wide peak observed in the XRD spectrum validated the amorphous nature of the synthesized particles, with particle sizes measuring 61 nm, 59 nm, 42 nm, and 34 nm. In FT-IR analysis, clear absorption peaks were observed, indicating that the nanoparticles were highly hygroscopic in nature. The metal oxygen Si-O bond is represented peak at 433 cm⁻¹, 439 cm⁻¹, 436 cm⁻¹, and 443 cm⁻¹. SEM image of SiO₂ nanoparticles showed the aggregated bundle like morphology. The electrochemical characteristics of SiO₂ nanoparticles have been investigated through cyclic voltammetry. The findings demonstrated specific capacitance values of 310 Fg⁻¹, 325 Fg⁻¹, 356 Fg⁻¹, and 340 Fg⁻¹ at a scan rate of 5 mVs⁻¹, indicating their potential use in supercapacitor applications.

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